

THE TRANSITION OF POPULAR FOLKLORE GENRES TO CHILDREN'S CULTURE: AN ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH EXAMPLES

Fayzulloyev Otabek Muhamadovich

Doctor of philosophy in philology, associate professor
BukhSU, professor of "Interfaculty foreign languages" department

Email: roginraz2015@gmail.com

Тел: +998 914105903

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Abstract: This article analyzes the genres that have passed from adult folklore to children's folklore in Uzbek and English traditions. Genres such as riddles, fairy tales and songs are considered an important tool for developing children's minds and instilling national values in them. The article extensively analyzes folklore works that influence children's spiritual and mental development.

Keywords: Adult folklore, children's folklore, Uzbek traditions, English traditions, riddles, fairy tales, songs, cultural heritage

Folklore is one of the most effective means of transmitting cultural heritage to generations. It includes a wide variety of genres of oral creativity that preserve the most ancient experiences, values and life knowledge of mankind. At the same time, there are genres in folklore that were first formed among adults, and later became popular among children, playing an important role in their spiritual and mental development. In Uzbek and English folklore, such genres, including riddles, fairy tales and songs, have a special place and are of great importance in children's education.

Riddles have been an important part of folklore since ancient times. Originally, riddles were used as a test of intelligence and ingenuity among adults. Through them, people sought to find hidden meanings, to understand the essence of everything. Uzbek and English riddles have a unique structure, and the role played by both nations in children's education is incomparable. For example, through the question "There is a boneless man standing behind the door", which is one of the English riddles, children are directed to understand the meaning of the language word. And in Uzbek riddles, "A thousand lamps in a pot, what is this?" such questions are an important tool in developing children's logical thinking. Such riddles encourage children to think deeply, find hidden meanings and strengthen their thinking skills.

Although fairy tales, with their historical roots, have taken an important place in the lives of adults, over time they have become children's favorite stories. During this process, fairy tales retained their educational and educational value. Uzbek and English folk tales are of great importance in educating the young generation, in their moral and spiritual development. One of the English folk tales, "Robin Hood" was first popular among adults, and later became popular among children. This tale plays a great role in promoting justice, courage and bravery. Among the Uzbek folk tales, stories such as "Zumrad va Qimmat" give children deep ideas about the negative consequences of hard work, tolerance and selfishness. These fairy tales are of great importance in conveying life lessons to children and forming positive qualities in them.

Songs are another genre that has become part of children's folklore. The songs that were originally performed by adults have been preserved over time in the form of amusement, entertainment and game songs that play an important role in the daily life of children. For example, in English children's folklore, songs like "Humpty Dumpty" were first in the form of riddles, and later in the form of songs. This song helps children learn simple rules and analytical skills.

In Uzbek children's folklore, songs such as "Boychechak" and "Yo Ramazan" are of great importance in teaching children about seasonal rituals. Through these songs, children learn their national values, traditions and concepts related to nature.

The migration of such genres from adult folklore to children's folklore not only ensures the continuity of cultural heritage, but also serves as an important tool for educating the younger generation and instilling national values in them. Through this process, children not only absorb the cultural heritage of the nation, but also become its successors. In the Uzbek and English traditions, the uniqueness of this process plays a major role in the preservation and development of national culture.

References:

1. Bronner, Simon J. «American Children's Folklore». Little Rock: August House, 1988.
2. Degh, Linda, and Andrew Vázsonyi. "The Dialectics of Legend." «Folklore Studies in Hungary» 3 (1973): 5-29.
3. Fine, Gary Alan. "Folklore Diffusion through Interactive Social Networks: Conduits in a Preadolescent Community." «New York Folklore Quarterly» 5 (1979): 25-41.
4. Jahongirov, G'afur. «O'zbek Xalq Ertaklari». Toshkent: Fan, 1984.

5. MacDowell, John H. «Children's Riddling». Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1979.
6. McDowell, John H. "The Poetics of Children's Riddling." «The Journal of American Folklore» 88.348 (1975): 301-314.
7. Thompson, Stith. «The Folktale». New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, 1946.
8. Zaripov, H. «O'zbek Bolalar Folklori». Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1980.
9. Sutton-Smith, Brian. «A History of Children's Play: From Gilgamesh to Shakespeare». New York: Crane, Russak, 1981.
10. Williams, David. «A Critical Study of Modern English Folklore». Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1966.

